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ABOUT THE OAEBU DATA TRUST EFFORT

Originating in 2015, the OAeBU Data Trust effort has brought over 100 individuals across five continents together to surface and address the issues that complicate the analysis and use of book usage metrics for decision making and open access advocacy. To date, the project has documented the complex OAeBU data supply chain,² launched pilots of open-source infrastructure for a usage data trust, and facilitated workshops to understand the ways in which scholars and specific staff roles at libraries, publishers, and publishing platforms and services rely on OAeBU data. While these use cases were documented to inform data trust service development, the project team recognizes that they provide broader insights into the evolving analytics and linked data demands across the scholarly communications ecosystem.

METHODOLOGY

This document evolved from the outputs of multiple virtual ideation sessions and workshops among peer stakeholder groups. These community-oriented feedback mechanisms were advertised via the OAeBU Data Trust effort's communities of practice. Co-Editors Drummond and Hawkins translated meeting and asynchronous ideation outputs into a preliminary use case document, which was shared back for public comment via the project's communities of practice and social media.³ Public comment was incorporated into this document, with notes offered by community members included at the end of each section. Within this document, staff roles at platforms and services that work with usage data are identified as personas. Then, use cases are listed with descriptions of why usage data is important or how it is applied for a given use case. Specific questions or queries of usage data that surfaced in discussion are noted.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Book publishers, publishing platforms and services, and libraries all rely on book usage data to inform their operations. Across these industries, staff must address the burden of managing and curating usage data provisioned in COUNTER-compliant and non-compliant reports,

1 https://educopia.org/data_trust/ and <https://zenodo.org/communities/oaebu>

2 Clarke, Michael, & Ricci, Laura. (2021, April 9). OA Books Supply Chain Mapping Report. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4681725>

3 The OAeBU project's processes for communities of practice development and use case development are published in Drummond, Christina (2020). "Engaging Stakeholder Networks to Support Global OA Monograph Usage Analytics," Collaborative Librarianship: Vol. 12 : Iss. 2 , Article 9. <https://digitalcommons.du.edu/collaborativelibrarianship/vol12/iss2/9>

APIs, dashboards, and spreadsheets. These institutions individually manage, compile, and link usage data metrics, some of which are provisioned via dashboard services for users ranging from scholars, research offices and funding agencies, to editors, collections and acquisitions managers, and administrative decision makers.

While the term “usage data” is often used today to refer to web analytics reports that tally page visits and file downloads, the use cases herein document a near future where linked usage data analytics regularly inform book publishing and scholarly communications operations. Publishers and libraries expressed interest in using OAeBU data analytics to inform overall investment, strategy and fundraising in OA programs. They noted how data on the location and context of access to OA eBooks can inform book marketing and dissemination strategy, acquisitions and collections development, and scholars’ promotion and tenure. OAeBU data also surfaced as vital to supporting the promotion of OA publication among scholars and to illustrating institutional impact on the local and global stage. Linked contextual usage data can illustrate how OA books reach targeted audiences in classrooms, among scholars, within industry, and among policy-makers.

OAeBU data is poised to inform customer service relationships as publishers and libraries seek to appreciate service provider niches, evaluate book hosting and dissemination arrangements, and understand what is returned from their OA investments. Simultaneously, publishing platforms and services leverage usage data to inform the research, development, sales, and marketing of their own infrastructure.

Diverse models of OA book publishers, from university or library-based publishers to commercial publisher OA teams, surfaced many common functional needs of OAeBU data for publishers as shown in the graphic below. However, their structures resulted in unique needs tied to administrative and sales reporting, as is reflected in their individual use cases.

BOOK PUBLISHING PLATFORMS AND SERVICES

OPEN ACCESS EBOOK USAGE (OAEBU) DATA USE CASES

A variety of book publishing platforms and services apply OAeBU data in support of internal operations and technical development while also provisioning it to meet their customers' demand for usage data reporting. Staff roles that may interact with OAeBU data span sales and marketing staff, business and data analysts, IT specialists, publisher relations staff, and community managers.

Challenges faced when working with OAeBU data arise from OAeBU data variability and the multiple processing approaches in use across the OAeBU data supply chain to manage issues relating to book vs. chapter level data, bot vs. human access, and duplicate downloads.

IT, Data Analysts, and Product Development

Customer or Member Support, Sales, and Business Development

Use Case 1.

Inform publishing platform or service marketing strategy and communications

Personas

Why | How

- a. Contextualize search engine traffic
- b. Evaluate Search Engine Optimization (SEO) efforts
- c. Understand usage tied to current events.
 - i.e. "When x happened, what happened to usage data?"
 - i. to provide custom usage reports based on keyword search, e.g. "immigration"
 - ii. to identify usage spikes in real time
 1. for the full OA collection
 2. for specific sub-collections
- d. Report to major funders, stakeholders

Use Case 2.

Inform publishing platform or service sales strategy

Personas

- a. Inform differential pricing based on usage levels
- b. Identify potential customers for particular services based on usage, e.g. specific levels of preservation service
 - i. by reporting aggregate usage by publisher
 - ii. by reporting aggregate usage for titles
 - iii. by reporting aggregate usage for chapters
- c. Report usage trends to other parts of the business, e.g. journals
 - i. by country and type of usage for a given discipline, to suggest relevant new titles
 - ii. by using chapter data to inform edited/special editions

Use Case 3.

Manage and curate usage data

Personas

a. Support usage data provision

- i. by combining usage data received from aggregators, customer or member publishers, and social media
- ii. by finding and addressing problems in usage data streams
 - a. when cleaning data in real time according to community established rules or standards, e.g. COUNTER
 - b. when supporting or developing AI that reviews incoming data
 - c. to clean data after the fact

b. Support data versioning, i.e. tracking the changes made during the “data cleaning” process

- i. by applying APIs from third party systems
- ii. to manage non-standardized usage data
- iii. to manage “bad behavior” or inconsistent approaches to usage data processing, recognizing inconsistency might result if non-standardized approaches are applied to data cleaning

c. Incorporate and apply usage data related definitions, attributes, and standards

- i. to develop open “clean” data, i.e. apply COUNTER processing data rules such as <https://www.projectcounter.org/code-of-practice-five-sections/7-processing-rules-underlying-counter-reporting-data/>
- ii. to identify missing data definitions and suggest data definitions extending the COUNTER code practice such as <https://www.projectcounter.org/code-of-practice-five-sections/11-extending-code-practice/>, i.e. notify COUNTER of missing data in current definitions for consideration in the next release

d. Implement APIs with third-party system delegates of customers or members to support analysis with non-usage data sources

e. Implement security and privacy controls for personal data within usage datasets such as IP addresses or individual identifiers

f. Document all steps, definitions, and preservation plan in usage data management plan to make data provenance transparent for system users

Use Case 4.

Facilitate technical development of platform or service

Personas

a. Develop usage data dashboards or visualizations

- i. to provide templates for commonly requested views
 1. of changes in library usage, i.e. OA book count represented on platform or service over time
 2. of changes in publisher usage of platform or service for OA, e.g. number of members using platform or service over time
 3. of languages represented in OA corpus over time
 4. of license versions represented in corpus over time
 5. of geographic usage
- ii. to provide custom usage data reports for customers or members
e.g. *"When x happened, what was the impact on usage?"*

b. Design, develop, and support usage-related platform or service features

- i. e.g. APIs that support member or customer demand
- ii. e.g. widgets or tools that collect usage-related data
- iii. to manage situation when members or customers define or process chapter or book level data differently
- iv. to manage situation when a book and its chapters, parts, or supplemental materials are hosted separately
- v. by understanding how users want to see reports rolled up

c. Evaluate how technical platform or service developments impact book usage and traffic

e.g. *"Did moving the download button improve usage?"*

d. Inform future development by understanding usage data related service or product demand by members or customers

- i. to develop potential financial use cases
- ii. by revealing previously unknown uses, users, and/or audiences

e. Inform or prompt an evaluation of why a service isn't being used

e.g. *"No one queries this specific API"*

f. Support risk management planning tied to demand surges by informing action plans to support temporary increase in demand for usage data

g. Inform strategies to manage and/or reduce costs associated with usage related to specific publication file types

Use Case 5.

Customer or member support and account management

Personas

"Common definitions tied to standards (e.g. COUNTER, ONIX, SUSHI) should be clear for DOI, book, chapter, audience, customer."

a. Support customer or member use of usage information

- i. for publishers
 1. to inform publisher staff interface for usage data, i.e. direct
 2. to support publishers' author interfaces for usage data, i.e. pass-through or white-label websites
 3. to help publishers understand how to use usage data once they obtain it
- ii. for discovery platforms
 1. to show how adding books to discovery platform impacts traffic back
 2. to manage demand on servers
 3. to understand how customers, members, and/or libraries are getting to books directly or via aggregators
 4. to understand impact if a book isn't on a certain platform or service
- iii. for authors seeking self-service
 1. by informing or providing author interfaces for usage data, i.e. direct
- iv. for libraries
 1. to support library interfaces for usage data, i.e. direct
 - a. by surfacing local use and impact
 - b. by showing local connections
 - i. by author affiliation
 - ii. to local geographic region
 2. to support librarians informing or driving local usage

b. Support customer or member evaluation of services or products based on usage

c. Support customer or member placing usage in historical or relative contexts

- i. to help them answer "How does Report A saying X compare to Report B saying Y?"
- ii. to explain limitations to data and aid data interpretation, i.e. "What does data mean and what does it not mean?"
 1. for longitudinal usage
 2. for usage relative to other media/content
 3. for usage relative to other platforms

d. Use usage data to help customer or member improve their own metadata

e. Support customer or member if or when usage surges

- i. by tracking usage surges by country
- ii. by tracking usage surges by customer or member

f. Understand how and where to grow additional customer or member support based on usage

- i. by identifying regions for internationalization
 1. of new, additional language support
 2. for increased regional customer or member support